

PRISMA: Disillusionment Among Young People in the University Context

Authors:

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Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	Title page (p.1)
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist.	Abstract (p.1)
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	Introduction (pp.2–3)
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	Introduction (pp. 3)
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	Methodology section (p.4)
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.	Methodology – Databases paragraph (p.4)
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	Methodology – Keyword string (p.4–5)
Selection process	8	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Methodology – Screening description (p.5)
Data collection process	9	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Methodology – Interpretive analysis (p.5)

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Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g. for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.	Methodology – Analytical categories (p.5)
	10b	List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g. participant and intervention characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.	Methodology – Secondary sources (p.4–5)
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Not applicable – Theoretical review (p.5)
Effect measures	12	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g. risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	Not applicable – No meta-analysis
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g. tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item #5)).	Methodology – Theoretical triangulation (p.5)
	13b	Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data conversions.	Methodology – Theoretical triangulation (p.5)
	13c	Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.	Methodology – Theoretical triangulation (p.5)

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	13d	Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.	Methodology – Theoretical triangulation (p.5)
	13e	Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results (e.g. subgroup analysis, meta-regression).	Methodology – Theoretical triangulation (p.5)
	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results.	Methodology – Theoretical triangulation (p.5)
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).	Not applicable – Qualitative design
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.	Not applicable – Narrative synthesis
RESULTS			
Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow diagram.	Results – PRISMA section
	16b	Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded.	PRISMA table
Study characteristics	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	Results discussion

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			(pp.6–12)
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	Not applicable – Narrative review
Results of individual studies	19	For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.	Results section (pp.6–12)
Results of syntheses	20a	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.	Results section (pp.6–12)
	20b	Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect.	Results section (pp.6–12)
	20c	Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	Results section (pp.6–12)
	20d	Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.	Results section (pp.6–12)
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.	Discussion (p.13)
Certainty of evidence	22	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	Discussion (pp.13–14)
DISCUSSION			
Discussion	23a	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.	Discussion (pp.13–14)

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	23b	Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.	Discussion (pp.13–14)
	23c	Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.	Discussion (pp.13–14) Discussion (pp.13–14)
	23d	Discuss implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	Discussion (pp.13–14) Discussion (pp.13–14)
OTHER INFORMATION			
Registration and protocol	24a	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number, or state that the review was not registered.	Not registered – stated in Methods
	24b	Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed, or state that a protocol was not prepared.	Not registered – stated in Methods
	24c	Describe and explain any amendments to information provided at registration or in the protocol.	Not registered – stated in Methods
Support	25	Describe sources of financial or non-financial support for the review, and the role of the funders or sponsors in the review.	Competing Interests / Funding (p.15)
Competing interests	26	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	Competing

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			Interests section (p.15)
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	Data Availability section (p.14)

PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for new systematic reviews which included searches of databases and registers only

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*Consider, if feasible to do so, reporting the number of records identified from each database or register searched (rather than the total number across all databases/registers).

**If automation tools were used, indicate how many records were excluded by a human and how many were excluded by automation tools.

Regarding the two points raised:

First, we did not report the number of records identified from each individual database separately because the search results from Web of Science and Scopus were exported and consolidated prior to screening. The review was conducted as an integrated qualitative synthesis rather than a comparative database analysis. Therefore, only the total number of records identified across databases ($n = 35$) is reported. Disaggregated counts per database were not retained during the consolidation process.

Second, no automation tools were used at any stage of the screening or selection process. All records were screened manually by the authors based on title, abstract, and full-text assessment. Consequently, there were no exclusions performed by automation tools, and all exclusions were conducted through human review.

We hope this clarification resolves the concern.